

Issue:

On the teaching of Language and Literature: reflections on epistemicide

Revista Letras Raras (RLR), a scholarly journal of Linguistics and Literature, published by the Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity — a research group linked to the Postgraduate Program in Language and Teaching from the Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG) —, launches its first issue of 2023. Meanwhile, the journal enters its 12th year, seeking to keep current discussions alive in the fields of Language and Literature studies.

This first issue of the 12th year of RLR circulation brings an indispensable theme to be considered in our days, which is “*On the teaching of Language and Literature: reflections on epistemicide*”. It is organised by PhD professors and researchers from Brazilian universities, such as professor Maria Angélica de Oliveira (UFCG) and professor Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz (UFCG), as well as professor Vima Lia de Rossi Martin, from the University of São Paulo (USP). Along the way, this theme is also the focus of studies at Charles University Prague, in the capital of the Czech Republic, represented by Professor Karolina Válková.

The research results presented here are the responsibility of researchers at various levels of education, from undergraduate students and beginner researchers to experienced professors from higher education institutions. Thereby, this issue features a significant diversity of origins of these scholars in the Language and Literature fields. Thus, it welcomes texts from these fellow researchers, undergraduate scientific research students, masters and doctoral students, as well as PhD scholars from the following universities: State University of Campinas (UNICAMP), Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), Federal University of Tocantins (UFT), La Salle University (UNILASALLE), Federal University of Alagoas (UFAL), Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), Federal University of Goiás (UFG), Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE), State University of São Paulo (UNESP), State University of the Central-West (UNICENTRO), State University of Paraná (UNESPAR), Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC), and University of Passo Fundo (FUPF).

Therefore, dear reader, this first issue of 2023 prompts reflection on the need to build a new episteme from the perspective of the Global South, considering that it is urgent to provide more visibility

to the Southern hemisphere. By this means, share the paper, interview, essay, and artistic productions of this issue with your colleagues and students.

We begin the series of publications for this year of 2023 with renewed hopes regarding more attention and support for the direction of research in our country. As we usually emphasise, it is our will that the texts published here incite tolerance, respect, equity, and a more science-centred education for all!

In the certainty of this sharing, dear reader, we wish you a great reading!

PhD Prof. Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz (UFMG, Brazil)

PhD Prof. Maria Rennally Soares da Silva (UEPB/UFMG, Brazil)

PhD Prof. Marco Antônio Margarido Costa (UFMG, Brazil)

Editors of **Revista Letras Raras**: a Scholarly Journal of the Research Group LELLC – Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity / Postgraduate Program in Language and Teaching / Federal University of Campina Grande

Translated by Rafael de Arruda Sobral